

MAPPING FUTURE FLOOD AND HEAT DISADVANTAGE IN GREAT BRITAIN:
AN ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF ADAPTATION POLICIES IN PROJECTED
HOTSPOTS AT A LOCAL SCALE

By

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Abstract

Climate change impacts are not distributed equally or fairly (“just”) and the need to focus adaptation efforts on socially vulnerable communities is increasingly recognized. This paper identifies and maps the top 30 heat and flood disadvantaged British local authorities using open-source data and it investigates the status of and reasons for lack of adaptation actions based on a literature review.

The results indicated relatively high to acute heat risks for the urban areas and high to extreme flood risks to numerous local authorities across Great Britain. While most authorities had climate action plans in place, the overall performance scores were low, only half had adaptation plans, and they lacked evidence on implementation. Funding and possibly knowledge gaps were identified as limiting factors and barriers to adaptation.

These results suggest that British local authorities not only need more adaptation plans, but they also need to implement them and monitor their success. This research can assist policy makers during the adaptation planning process by allocating financial resources to those in need, with the goal to increase their resilience to future climate change impacts.

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Mapping future flood and heat disadvantage in Great Britain: An analysis of the current state of adaptation policies in projected hotspots at a local scale

Climate change is a global phenomenon, and its impacts vary greatly by scale and region. Increasing global temperatures, combined with heavier local rainfall will further increase flood risks in Europe, and the United Kingdom (UK) is likely to be among the hardest hit, significantly increasing their annual cost of flooding (Pidcock, 2014). Already 335 local authorities in the UK have declared a 'climate emergency' (Climate Emergency UK, n.d.).

Many countries worldwide have implemented national climate policies to reduce impacts and risks of climate change (Arnwell et al., 2021). The Climate Change Act 2008 commits the UK government to climate action and to adapt to climate change (Climate Change Committee, n.d.). Yet, while the UK has been leading the international Resilience and Adaptation Call for Action (Arnwell et al., 2021), the Climate Change Committee (CCC) (2021a) warned that the UK government was “falling behind on adapting to climate change” (p.14).

For climate actions to be effective, they must be a combination of mitigation strategies (e.g., reducing greenhouse gas emissions), and adaptation strategies (helping society to adjust), where adaptation is needed, to help reduce the remaining risks of climate impacts that have not been avoided by mitigation (CCC, 2021a; Füssel, 2007; IPCC, 2014). The severity of impacts depends on the level of vulnerability and hazard-exposure (Cardona et al., 2012); therefore, understanding and identifying areas of increased vulnerability and risk ('hotspots') is critical to assist with adaptation actions (National Research Council, 2010).

This research paper identifies local authorities (LAs) with the greatest future heat disadvantage in England and the greatest future flood disadvantage in Great Britain (GB). An

analysis of climate actions in those hotspots evaluates the status of adaptation actions, climate action performances, and suggests reasons for gaps in the adaptation process.

Research Context and Purpose

The need for this research paper was prompted when my British work colleagues contacted me with the idea to map and analyze the most socially vulnerable communities for a series of thought leadership on the impact of climate change on weather, migration, and urbanization. Stakeholders within public and private institutions increasingly need spatial information of social vulnerability at the local scale, that indicates to spatial planning what interventions are needed and where, thus helping facilitate adaptation policies (Preston et al., 2011).

This research could benefit decision making processes for urban heat management with respect to additional locations of urban vegetation, increased perviousness, and surface reflectivity (Vargo et al., 2016); it could show practitioners how some people and places are affected differently than others and potentially stimulate fiscal interventions through the UK levelling up agenda, Green Industrial Revolution and Government's Build Back Better (Stantec, personal communication, August 12, 2021); and ideally, it may contribute to achieving the sustainable development goals (SDGs) 11 and 13.

Moreover, a disconnect has been found between the mapping of vulnerability and achieved adaptive responses addressing it (Preston et al., 2011). Mapping the most socially vulnerable British communities and analyzing the state of adaptation policies in vulnerability hotspots, can help highlight the LAs in need for adaptation, raise awareness about the need for increased adaptation actions (Hammill et al., 2013), and potentially demonstrate the need for more research to be conducted.

Research Questions

Vulnerability varies across people and places, with some being more susceptible to climate change impacts than others. Adaptation strategies can address inequities and may help to achieve climate justice. To help address socially just climate actions, this paper addresses two research questions.

1. With respect to socio-spatial heat and flood risks, where are the top 30 most disadvantaged local authorities in England and Great Britain, respectively?
2. What is the state of adaptation actions in hotspots and what are possible reasons for adaptation gaps?

Objectives

This research paper comprises of three interconnected parts. First, using open-source geospatial data, vulnerability and future social climate risks were mapped and analyzed to identify and rank the top 30 disadvantaged LAs (hotspots) with respect to heat and flood. The results were summarized and presented in tables and maps.

Second, a literature review of national 'grey' literature was conducted to evaluate the status and performance of adaptation actions in the hotspots, i.e., action plans or strategies that were in place or planned. Their locations were digitized and overlaid with the hotspots to analyze links between high vulnerability and adaptation actions, and to gain a better understanding of the spatial distribution of mitigation and adaptation actions.

Third, a review of national and international academic literature helped to learn background information and understand reasons for adaptation gaps. The results are not without limitations, and a description of encountered problems and limitations was included.

Literature Review

In 2020, the UK recorded its third warmest year on record, its fifth-driest spring, and local daily precipitation that almost reached $\frac{3}{4}$ of the monthly normal, resulting in high river levels and flooding (Bissolli et al., 2021). Likewise, Lowe et al. (2018) predicted a continuation of this trend. They expect the greatest warming in the southern UK, where temperatures in summer could increase by 0.9°C to 5.4°C by 2070 (high emission scenario). For the same emission scenario, precipitation could increase by up to 35% in winter and decrease by up to 47% in summer (Lowe et al., 2018).

With changing UK weather, climate hazards, such as extreme temperatures, increased floods, and extreme coastal water levels, could worsen, both in frequency and magnitude (Lowe et al., 2018). Extreme events have greater impacts on sectors such as “water, agriculture and food security, forestry, health, and tourism” (IPCC, 2012, p. 16). Extreme heat can impact human health, increase the heat island effect, damage infrastructure (e.g., buckling of rail tracks and pipe distress due to soil moisture changes), decrease aircraft performance, increase water, heating, and cooling demands, and increase wildfire risks (Arnwell et al., 2021; Lowe et al., 2018). The immediate impacts of flooding are well known and may include loss of human life and livestock, damage of property and crops, and damage to infrastructure. In 2020, flooding in the UK also caused major disruptions in public transport (Bissolli et al., 2021).

Climate change is a global issue and hence must be addressed by “multiple actors, across multiple levels of governance” (Sainz de Murieta & Setzer, 2019, p. 5). While there are international agreements on climate change and the Paris Agreement defines a “global goal on adaptation” (UNFCCC, n.d., para. 2), this does not imply the same efforts at a local level (IPCC, 2012).

Moreover, while mitigation and adaptation should be considered and integrated together to address climate change (CCC, 2021a; Füssel, 2007), “scientifically and from a policy perspective . . . mitigation has traditionally received much greater attention” (Füssel, 2007, p. 265). However, adaptation actions are equally important because their “characteristic time-scales and the actors concerned are largely distinct” from mitigation actions (Füssel, 2007, p. 266). Moreover, even with drastically reduced emissions, the sea level will continue to rise for another century (Lowe et al., 2018), and without adaptation strategies, climate impacts will increase drastically across the UK (Arnwell et al., 2021; CCC, 2021a; Pidcock, 2014).

UK Climate Legislation and Government Structure

The Climate Change Act 2008 provides the policy framework that aims to reduce domestic emissions, addresses climate adaptation, and it requires the government to provide a Climate Change Risk Assessment (CCRA), with current and future climate risks and opportunities, every five years (CCC, n.d.). The Act also established the CCC and its Adaptation Sub-Committee (ASC) and requires them to provide advice on the CCRA to the UK Government (CCC, n.d.). Following the CCRA publication, each UK nation must prepare a National Adaptation Plan (National Adaptation Programme in England) with objectives and policies on how to address those risks and opportunities identified in the CCRA (CCC, n.d.).

The Department for Business, Energy, and Industrial Strategy (BEIS) is responsible for mitigation policy and promoting climate action and the Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (Defra), is responsible for climate adaptation policy and developing the National Adaptation Programme (CCC, n.d.). While flood risk policies across England, Wales, and Scotland “refer to reducing vulnerability”, only England has “formal mechanism for targeting

investment towards the most vulnerable neighbourhoods”, and despite some success in England, nationwide “disadvantage remains significant” (Sayers et al., 2017, p. viii).

At a local level, the Act does not require LAs to act on climate change (CCC, 2020). Moreover, competing policies and programs, i.e., in areas of housing and transport (CCC, 2020), and limited resources, prevent LAs to effectively deliver climate action and are “a constraint on implementing adaptation actions” (CCC, 2021a, p. 112). Responsibilities and powers depend on the type of LA and the country where it is located (UK Government, 2021). Today, there are 333 LAs in England (including 10 combined authorities), and while most of them are two-tier authorities (i.e., county councils and district, borough, or city councils), some are single-tier authorities, such as London (32 boroughs and City of London), other metropolitan areas, and parts of shire England (UK Government, 2021). Wales has 22 unitary authorities (Wales Government, n.d.), and Scotland has 32 local authorities (Scotland Government, n.d.). This paper uses 'local authority' or 'LA' to address any type of authority or council at a local level in England, Wales, and Scotland (Figure 1).

Definition of Terms

This research adopted IPCCs definitions given by Oppenheimer et al. (2014), where *hazard* is a potential climate-related event or impact that may negatively affect health or fundamental facilities, systems, or services. While they defined *exposure* as “the presence . . . in places and settings that could be adversely affected” (p. 5), *vulnerability* is the tendency “to be adversely affected” (p. 5), and *risk* as the “potential for consequences . . . [because of] the interaction of vulnerability, exposure, and hazard” (Oppenheimer et al., 2014).

The authors defined *adaptation* as “process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects” (p. 5) and *resilience* as the “capacity of social, economic, and environmental

systems to cope [with hazards and impacts] . . . in ways that maintain their essential function, identity, and structure” (Oppenheimer et al., 2014, p. 5). *Adaptive capacity* is the ability to adjust and respond (Jones et al., 2014). *Maladaptation* is an “intervention in one sector [that] could increase vulnerability of another sector or increase the vulnerability of a group to future climate change” (p. 859), for example, actions that are giving a false sense of security and thereby reducing the preparedness to future risks (Noble et al., 2014).

Risk, Exposure, and Vulnerability

Marginalized people are particularly vulnerable to climate change and even some adaptation and mitigation actions, and “skewed development processes such as those associated with environmental degradation, rapid and unplanned urbanization in hazardous areas, [and] failures of governance”, can further exacerbate their exposure and vulnerability (IPCC, 2012, p.10), for example, the continued development of homes on floodplains (Sayers et al., 2017). Exposure and vulnerability depend on non-climatic factors and inequalities, caused by social processes such “levels of wealth and education, disability, and health status, as well as gender, age, class, and other social and cultural characteristics” (IPCC, 2012, p.19).

Whereas the climate affects the current and future climate hazards, socio-economic changes and adaptation measures influence exposure and vulnerability (Arnwell et al., 2021). Climate risk, especially for vulnerable areas and groups, can be successfully reduced by implementing adaptation strategies, including “disaster risk in national development and sector plans” (IPCC, 2012, p.10). However, a “blanket response on the basis of hazard-exposure alone” may benefit those with better resources more than the socially vulnerable (Lindley et al., 2011, p. 1). Also, because adaptation measures can reduce short-term risks but also may increase long-term exposure and vulnerability, the “temporal and spatial dynamics” of exposure and

vulnerability need to be understood (IPCC, 2012, p.94). For example, “dike systems can reduce flood exposure by offering immediate protection, but also encourage settlement patterns that may increase risk in the long term” (IPCC, 2012, p.94).

Risk and Vulnerability Assessment

To help understand potential effects of climate change and extreme events on a system, climate change risk and vulnerability assessments have been used by decision makers for identifying mitigation and adaptation measures and vulnerable regions or groups to better channel resource allocation for research and adaptation (Füssel & Klein, 2006).

Although they help to communicate adaptation strategies, they need to focus more on adaptation and less on the impacts (Jones et al., 2014). Additionally, monitoring, evaluation, and the effectiveness of adaptation in risk assessments need to be considered more (Adger et al., 2018). Furthermore, a common approach, especially by governments, has been the use of indicators based on socio-economic variables (social indicators such as income) of a system (e.g., a community) to predict their vulnerability to climate impacts; however, many methods used, need to be improved due to a “lack of validation frameworks and the [use of an] unjustified equal-weighting approach” (Barankin et al., 2021, p. 8; Hinkel, 2011).

Heat Disadvantage

Translating environmental, personal, and social factors into indicators and combining them into socio-spatial vulnerability scores, can help identify locations of very high vulnerability and it can improve understanding of uneven distribution of vulnerabilities (Figure 2) (Lindley et al., 2011). Moreover, when vulnerability is intersected with potential hazard-exposure, neighbourhoods with the greatest social heat risk or heat disadvantage can be identified, and thus, the locations with the greatest need for adaptation efforts (Figure 3) (Lindley et al. 2011).

Flood Disadvantage

Combining characteristics of vulnerability and vulnerability indicators into a flood vulnerability index, can help understand the social flood vulnerability of a neighbourhood (Figure 4) (Sayers et al., 2017). There are four types of floods, fluvial (river), coastal, surface water (pluvial), and groundwater flooding, whereas groundwater flooding is less common, difficult to assess, and thus “of low importance” (Sayers et al., 2017, p. 14). When intersecting the most vulnerable neighbourhoods and frequent exposure to flooding, the social flood risk or flood disadvantage can be identified (Figures 5 and 6) (Sayers et al., 2017).

Inequalities and Climate Justice

Greenhouse gases are not created equally, and climate impacts are not distributed equally (Lindley, 2011). Therefore, those climate impacts have potential effects not only on poverty and development but also on inequality (Islam & Winkel, 2017). Similarly, Chambwera et al. (2014) warned that climate change “exacerbates inequalities” and that “socially and economically disadvantaged and marginalized people are disproportionately affected by climate change” (p. 796). Moreover, on the subnational level, some local economic settings increase inequalities and consequently vulnerability to climate impacts (Sayers et al., 2017). For example, while most cities increasingly grow, some regions decline, often causing unemployment and low “social provision” (Sayers et al., 2017. p. 30).

To address the growing demand for a “just transition” and “climate justice” (CCC, 2021a, p. 98), effective adaptation actions should reduce the risk for disadvantaged communities and narrow regional inequality (in line with the Government’s Levelling Up agenda) by targeting “support to the households and communities most at risk”, and concurrently mitigation efforts should ensure a just transition to Net Zero (CCC, 2021a, p.98). Additionally, there is a need to

shift to a more “solidaristic insurance scheme” because the current “risk-differentiated regime” in the UK causes previously affected household or those at higher flood risks to lose their insurance or to have “prohibitively high premiums” (Lindley et al., p. 98).

Adaptation

The need and benefit of adaptation are increasingly recognized, e.g., that the number of risks – currently costing £billions per year – could otherwise triple by the 2080s (CCC, 2021a). Despite its benefits, adaptation financing has been topic of many debates. Chambwera et al. (2014) described the cost of adaptation as “the cost of any additional investment needed to adapt to or exploit future climate change” (p. 952) and its benefits as “the reduction in damages plus any gains in climate-related welfare that occur following an adaptation action” (p. 952). While knowledge of adaptation options, costs, and benefits is important, building adaptive capacity is “crucial for effective selection and implementation of adaptation options” (IPCC, 2014, p. 80).

Adaptation Assessment

To identify effective adaptation strategies, it is necessary to assess climate risks (risk assessments), vulnerability to the risks (vulnerability assessments), and adaptation needs and options to reduce the risks (adaptation assessment) (Noble et al., 2014). However, most of the conducted adaptation assessments have been limited “to impacts, vulnerability, and adaptation planning” (p. 837), and while decision makers have gained a better understanding “of climate risks and adaptation needs and options”, very few initiated actual adaptation actions (Noble et al., 2014, p. 837).

Adaptation Progress in the UK

Adaptation efforts in the UK began two decades ago, mainly by the government, with research into climate impacts, which then led to actions in “public agencies, regulatory agencies

and regional government” (Tompkins, 2010, p. 627). While sectors with large scale infrastructure (e.g., water supply and flood defence) were the main “early adopters of adaptation practice”, all other sectors and the local government showed little progress (Tompkins, 2010, p. 627). Reasons for adopting climate measures were “co-benefits. . . . sustainable development standards, EU legislation, perceived and real climate change impacts, risk management initiatives and conservation practices” (Tompkins, 2010, p. 633).

Today, globally “79 per cent of countries have addressed adaptation at the national level through a plan, strategy, policy or law” (Adaptation Gap Report 2021, p. 18), including the UK. However, at the subnational level, governments are often faced with challenges in “planning . . . implementing, and . . . monitoring, reporting and evaluating” climate adaptation actions (Sainz de Murieta & Setzer, 2019, p. 4). A research project conducted in the greater London area showed that “public bodies are taking action to first acknowledge the climate emergency and then thinking about what action to take” (City University, 2021, p. 5). They found that 86% of London councils declared a climate emergency, many had ambitious mitigation plans, and some implemented them; however, regarding climate adaptation and resilience strategies, most London councils “did not appear to have publicly available plans” (City University, 2021, p. 4).

Barriers to Adaptation

Barriers to adaptation can be competing policies, competing uses of limited resources (Chambwera et al., 2014; Fussel, 2007), and knowledge deficits (Porter, 2015). The greater focus on mitigation is explained with its (long-term) benefits and ease of monitoring, whereas the “effectiveness of proactive adaptation” is uncertain (Füssel, 2007, p. 265).

Other suggested reasons for the adaptation gap are “the public good nature of threatened resources; a failure in collective decision-making; and uncertainty over information interfering

with adaptation decisions”, and finally, unclear distribution of responsibilities and tasks (Tompkins & Adger, 2005, as cited in Tompkins et al., 2010, p. 628). Similarly, some scholars criticized that adaptation policies are limited by “cultures of risk denial” and that “governments do not deal well with so-called creeping environmental problems” (Glantz, 1999; Moser, 2005; as cited in Tompkins et al., 2010, p. 629), while some found that public demand after high-profile events, such as flooding, were needed for the government to act (Arnell et al., 1984; Penning-Rowsell et al., 2006; as cited in Tompkins et al., 2010, p. 629)

Methods

This research paper combines (a) a literature review as theoretical foundation to gain knowledge on background information and to understand reasons for adaptation gaps, (b) descriptive research using quantitative data analysis of secondary data to identify the most disadvantaged LAs (hotspots), and (c) a mixed methods approach using a semi-systematic literature review to identify adaptation actions, and a qualitative data analysis of primary descriptive data, to evaluate adaptation actions. Figure 7 shows the analytical framework used for this study; details are discussed in the following sections.

Literature Review on Background Information and Adaptation Gaps

The aim of the literature review was to gain knowledge on background information, such as context regarding the government structure in the UK, assessments of risk factors and adaptation, adaptation gaps, previous studies on the topic, and any study gaps. Several procedures were followed to ensure a credible and reproducible review of literature. Relevant data sources were identified from Royal Roads University’s library and 'grey literature' from Google Scholar and Google, and the search was restricted to sources published between 2006 and 2021. Credibility was ensured by including primarily peer reviewed data sources; however,

findings from grey literature were included to draw information from technical and research reports, and governments.

Search Strategies

Multiple search terms and Boolean logic combinations were used for the search with three search engines, the RRU library, Google Scholar, and Google (Appendix A).

Procedure

First, for each of the searches, titles or abstracts of the first 30 search returns of each search engine were screened. 187 papers identified as relevant were selected for further evaluation. Second, sources were evaluated, and abstracts were screened to confirm they met study inclusion criteria for each specific search purpose. Their reference section was searched to find additional relevant sources. Studies opposing my opinion were also included, to avoid biased results. Third, papers and information of the final selection were organized, documented, and findings were abstracted.

Mapping Hotspots and Data Analysis

To map the top 30 most disadvantaged LAs, secondary data from Climate Just (Climate Just, n.d.) and the Office for National Statistics (ONS, n.d.) was accessed. Both are open-source data, that will allow others to reproduce maps. All data was available in Excel tables (or .csv format) and GIS shapefile format and could be used in the ESRI ArcGIS 10.8.1 environment without conversion.

The geospatial data was at a neighbourhood scale; however, the basis for all the mapping and analysis needed to be local authority scale, which is the lowest tier of local government and the spatial unit used for the climate actions. The spatial data accessed was made up of z-scores and categorical data at neighbourhood-scale. To show the results at the LA scale, it needed to be

reduced without losing underlying components of information. Some techniques (e.g., median split), categorize continuous data; however, they may generalize data too much (Grace-Martin, n.d.). For this research, the categorical data has been ranked; however, different ranking methods may change the ranking order (Lindley et al., 2011).

The spatial data used for the LA boundaries was 2017 Local Authority District (LAD17) data (ONS, n.d.), to match the heat and flood data; however, today 2021 local authority district data is used, and since 2017, several LAs had merged. To avoid duplicated counts of climate performance data, those merged LAs were only considered for ranking but not for results on climate plan performances. The top 30 most disadvantaged LA have been identified for four heat and four flood scenarios and they added up to a total of 85 LAs.

Study Areas

At the time of access, Climate Just provided spatial heat vulnerability and disadvantage data for England and flooding vulnerability and risk data for England, Wales, and Scotland (Climate Just, n.d.). Therefore, the study area for heat disadvantage is England and the study areas for flood disadvantage is Great Britain (Figure 1).

Scenarios

The first set of four scenarios shows the hotspots for heat disadvantage in England, for (a) average (mean) and (b) neighbourhood-weighted vulnerability, and for two medium-emission temperature scenarios, (c) mean summer maximum temperature in the 2050s, and (d) change in mean summer maximum temperature baseline to 2050), both medium (M50) emission scenarios (Climate Just, n.d.). For neighbourhood-weighted vulnerability, means were multiplied by the number of neighbourhoods in each 25 km cell of the hazard-exposure data, to identify areas

“where both means and neighbourhood numbers come together to give high aggregate scores” (Lindley et al., 2011, p. 171).

The second set of four scenarios shows hotspots for flood disadvantage in GB for a 2050s 4°C global mean temperature rise scenario (assuming continuing adaptation efforts and high population growth), (a) as neighbourhood scale 'group' measure (SFRI) and (b) as 'individual' scale measure (iSFRI), i.e., normalized by population, and for two flood themes, (c) coastal and fluvial flooding combined, and (d) pluvial flooding (Climate Just, n.d.). Groundwater flooding has not been considered.

Heat Data Procedure

The spatial heat disadvantage data was the result of an assessment of social vulnerability in 2011 and data of hazard-exposure to heat, using 2009 UK Climate Projections (UKCP09) (Climate Just, n.d.) at a local scale (Middle Super Output Areas [MSOA]) (Lindley et al., 2011). The conceptual framework for assessing socio-spatial vulnerability and climate disadvantage, and an illustration of the relationships between the different datasets can be found in Appendix B (Lindley et al., 2011).

For the heat analysis work, two future hazard-exposure scenarios were used for two vulnerability measures, to create heat disadvantage ranks. First, vulnerability data (Climate Just, n.d.) and LAD17 boundary data (ONS, n.d.) were accessed, in ArcGIS, their projection and coverage confirmed, and they were spatially joined. Then the LAD17 name was assigned to each neighbourhood. Second, disadvantage data was only available in the Climate Just Map tool (Climate Just, n.d.). Therefore, images of four different future scenarios have been geo-referenced, digitized, and disadvantage attributes (i.e., z-scores and categories) were assigned according to the classification scheme (slight -3.5 to -2.5, extremely low -2.5 to -1.5, relatively

low -1.5 to -0.5, average -0.5 to 0.5, relatively high 0.5 to 1.5, extremely high 1.5 to 2.5, and acute 2.5 to 14). Third, vulnerability data was spatially joined with the newly created disadvantage data, and disadvantage attributes were assigned. Fourth, the attribute table of the vulnerability data was exported to Excel, and the Pivot table function used to calculate the ranks of the LAs. Fields used were LAD17 names, average z-scores, count of neighbourhoods, and filters used were disadvantage z-scores >0.5 and vulnerability categories relatively high, extremely high, and acute disadvantage. Because the exposure data (and thus, the disadvantage data) was at a 25 km scale, it would include neighbourhoods with lower vulnerability as well. Therefore, the filters were used to identify only highly vulnerable neighbourhoods with high exposure risk. The ranks of disadvantaged LAs were established by calculating the neighbourhoods most at risk as a proportion of the total number of neighbourhoods within each LA (Tables 1 and 2). Fifth, in ArcGIS, the ranks were joined (by LAD17 name) with the LAD17 boundary data, and the heat ranks were assigned.

Flood Data Procedure

The geospatial data of social vulnerability to flooding (fluvial, coastal, and surface water) and future flood disadvantage was based on an assessment of flood hazard, exposure, and vulnerability at neighbourhood scale (Lower Layer Super Output Areas [LSOA]), conducted by Sayers et al. (2017). For present and future risk calculations, they used the Future Flood Explorer (FFE). Components of their framework can be found in Appendix B.

For the flood analysis work, the 2050s future scenario was used for two vulnerability measures and two flood themes (four scenarios), to create flood disadvantage ranks. First, vulnerability and disadvantage data (Climate Just, n.d.) were accessed, in ArcGIS, their projection and coverage confirmed, and the disadvantage data was spatially joined with the

LAD17 boundary data from the heat analysis. Then the LAD17 name was assigned to each neighbourhood. Second, the attribute table of disadvantage data was exported to Excel, and the Pivot table function used to calculate the ranks of the LAs for all four scenarios. Fields used were LAD17 names, disadvantage categories, and count of neighbourhoods, and filters used were disadvantage categories high, very high, acute, and extreme risk. The ranks of disadvantaged LAs were established by calculating the neighbourhoods most at risk as a proportion of the total number of neighbourhoods within each LA (Tables 3 and 4). Third, in ArcGIS the ranks were joined (by LAD17 name) with the LAD17 boundary data, and the flood ranks were assigned.

Analysis of Adaptation Actions in Hotspots

A mixed methods approach was used to analyze adaptation action in hotspots. Using a literature review of grey literature, current or planned climate actions of the 85 most disadvantaged LAs were explored (qualitative method). Then, in ArcGIS, the locations were digitized and intersected with the hotspots to identify any links between vulnerability and climate actions. Key sources of information included government websites of all disadvantaged LAs and Climate Emergency UK (n.d.-a)

Search Strategies

Multiple search terms and Boolean logic combinations were used for the comprehensive search; only Google was used as source because primarily government websites were targeted (Appendix A).

Procedure

The semi-systematic literature review was conducted between January 4 and February 11, 2022. First, the government homepages of all 85 LAs were accessed, evaluated, and screened for action plans and strategies (mitigation and adaptation), to identify who was adapting to climate

change (Appendix C). A checklist with five categories was used to mark against certain criteria (0 not evident/ sufficient, 1 No, but in progress, and 2 Yes) (Appendix D). 218 documents, such as action plans, strategies, and policies, were identified as relevant and selected for further evaluation. Second, data was cross-checked and supplemented with data from the Climate Action Plan Explorer, an open database with collected UK Council Climate Action Plans (Climate Emergency UK, n.d.-b). Third, data was cross-checked and supplemented with climate action performance data from the Council Climate Plan Scorecards (Climate Emergency UK, n.d.-a), which were the result of a Britain-wide research conducted between June and December 2021 by Climate Emergency UK (n.d.), using an expert-approved checklist with 28 questions across nine sections to assess plans (Appendix E). Fourth, all data was compiled in Excel, and analyzed, i.e., absolute numbers, mean values, and low performances were determined, and mitigation, adaptation and governance/funding data were normalized and compared (Figures 16 and 19). Fifth, in ArcGIS, the final data was spatially joined with the LAD17 boundary containing the flood and heat data for visualization (Figures 8 to 15).

Results

Top 30 Hotspots and Their Adaptation Actions

Heat disadvantage was mapped for England, and the LAs ranked by the percentage of highly vulnerable neighbourhoods, with high to extreme risk of hazard-exposure, to the number of neighbourhoods in that LA (for four scenarios). For flood disadvantage, the study area was extended to GB. The top 30 disadvantaged LAs of each of the eight heat and flood scenarios combined to 85 different LAs across England, Wales, and Scotland. Of those 85 LAs, 57% had combined heat and flood disadvantages. For example, Hammersmith and Fulham ranked in the top 20 for all eight heat and flooding scenarios.

Heat Disadvantage

The top 30 heat disadvantaged LAs in England were presented on four figures, which also show the LAs' adaptation plans statuses (Figures 8 to 11). The greater London area was most disadvantaged, accounting for 60% of the hotspots for the first three scenarios and 77% for scenario 4, followed by Forest Heath, Nottingham, and the urban West Midlands, i.e., Birmingham, Sandwell, and Coventry (Tables 1 and 2). The LAs ranking in the top 15 for all four scenarios were the LAs in the London area (ranks 1-15), Forest Heath (rank 5), Nottingham (ranks 9 and 10), and Birmingham (ranks 13-15).

Heat disadvantage for LAs with average (simple mean) vulnerability (Figures 8 and 10) and neighbourhood-weighted vulnerability (Figures 9 and 11) were very similar (regardless of temperature patterns); however, representing vulnerability averages highlighted some disadvantaged locations with lower population densities, such as Cambridge, Forest Heath, Leicester, Luton, Middleborough, Oxford, Wolverhampton, and York (scenarios 1 and 2). The two temperature-patterns (maximum and change in temperature) also resulted in similar heat disadvantages, apart from Middlesbrough (rank 28), which was furthest north and only revealed for a combination of average vulnerability and change in temperature pattern (scenario 2).

Flood Disadvantage

Using a Social Flood Risk Index (SFRI), the top 30 flood disadvantaged LAs in GB were presented on four figures, which also show the LAs' adaptation plan statuses (Figures 12 to 15). Boston ranked at the top for all four scenarios, with 92-100% of Boston's neighbourhoods having high to extreme flood risks. For the remaining LAs, the results varied greatly depending on area and scenario.

For fluvial (river) and costal flooding and 'group' measure (scenario 1) (Figure 12), most disadvantaged LAs were in Lincolnshire and The Humber area (Boston, East Lindsey, and Hull), around the Bristol channel (i.e., West Somerset and Rhondda Cynon Taf), London, and the southeast coast (i.e., Shepway). For scenario 3 (Figure 13), the 'individual' scale measure (normalized by population) was used, which identified LAs with a high flood disadvantage but a smaller population. While the previously mentioned areas were still represented, in addition Isle of Anglesey, and the Scottish eastern Lowland (i.e., East Ayrshire and Dumfries and Galloway) made the top 30 list (Tables 3).

A similar picture emerged for surface water flooding. For the 'group' measure (scenario 2) (Figure 14) and the 'individual' scale measure (scenario 4) (figure 15), similar areas as before were still disadvantaged; however, for scenario 4 (individual), the locations of some of the most disadvantaged LAs shifted to the Scottish Lowland (except for Boston), which now represented 1/3 of all disadvantaged LAs ranking from 6 to 30 (Tables 4).

Climate Action Performances and State of Climate Actions

Britain-wide *climate action performances* were determined using the Council Climate Plan Scorecards (Climate Emergency UK, n.d.-a) and the *state of climate actions* was based on the government literature review. In GB, of 380 LAs (in 2017), 23 were not considered for the action performance results because they have merged into other LAs since then; none of them were hotspots.

Of the remaining 357 LAs, 80% had some form of climate action plan or strategy (mitigation and adaptation) in place, while 71 LAs had no plan or strategy by February 2022. For scorecard performance results, LAs without a plan were not considered to get a better idea of the performances of the LAs with scorecards. With respect to scorecard section 2 (mitigation and

adaptation), when comparing the normal distributions, a relationship was found between governance, development, and funding (section 1) and climate action measures (Figure 16).

There was also a spatial relationship, where, for 73% of the LAs, the performances for both sections stayed in a range of 20%, e.g., if an LA had a high performance in section 1, it also had a high performance in section 2 (Figure 17). For section 2, only 7% of the LAs had a performance score of 0% and all 286 LAs together scored a performance average of 48%.

Results for Hotspots

For the analysis of the state of adaptation actions in the 85 most disadvantaged LAs, climate action performance scores for sections 1 to 4 were presented, with mitigation and adaptation split up into separate results. Additionally, five categories were listed, representing the results from the literature review (Table 5). The performance scorecards for sections 5 to 9 were also provided (Table 6).

Based on the literature review, of the 85 LAs, 77 LAs (91%) had climate action measures in place with varying performances, 85% had declared a climate emergency, 51% participated in some other adaptation actions (independently of action plan status), such as community groups, case studies, or flood defence schemes, and 73% offered a website that was easy to navigate and helpful regarding climate change. In general, for adaptation actions, there was much more focus on flood resilience than on heat adaptation. In respect to climate action performance, one section not relating to action plans was noteworthy and indicated low performances across GB. For the section education, skills, and training, about 41% of LAs had a climate performance score less than 20%, and of those 26% had a score of 0%.

In total 42% of the LAs had no adaptation measures in place, while 9% of those were working on adaptation strategies. In comparison, only 9% of the LAs had no mitigation action

plans or strategies, while of those 4% were working on it. When comparing action performances, 51% of the LAs had performance scores less than 13% (1/8) for adaptation, and only 16% had scores less than 10% (1/10) for mitigation. Moreover, of the 70 LAs with adaptation measures, 34% had a performance score of 0%, versus 9% for mitigation, showing that LAs focused about four times more on mitigation both performance-wise and by absolute numbers of action plans. Regarding implementation of climate action plans into existing policies and procedures (section commitment and integration), while the average performance was 54%, 21% of the LAs had performance scores less than 14%. Specific results for just adaptation were not available.

For adaptation, the average climate action performance score was 29% versus 57% for mitigation. Climate performances were on average better for mitigation. This is especially noticeable in the Greater London area (Figure 18). When comparing the normal distributions of mitigation, adaptation, and governance, development, and funding, the uneven distribution is clearly noticeable (Figure 19). Also, for LAs with higher performance scores (>60%) for governance/funding, half of those LAs had similar performances for mitigation and adaptation and the other half clearly focused on mitigation instead. For LAs with lower performance scores (<50%) for governance/funding, the majority focused on mitigation. It should be noted that less than a quarter of the performance score for section 1 is allocated towards costs and funding, thus a high performance does not translate into low funding challenges.

Discussion

The impacts of climate change pose a higher risk for socially vulnerable communities. Identifying the most disadvantaged LAs can help during the adaptation planning process by allocating financial resources to those in need, to increase their resilience to climate change impacts (National Research Council, 2010). Therefore, to help address socially just climate

actions, this paper spatially represented the locations of the 30 most heat and flood disadvantaged LAs at a local scale for England and GB, respectively, and analysed their state of adaptation actions or lack thereof.

Regarding heat risks, by far most disadvantaged LAs were in the greater London area, followed by Forest Heath, Nottingham, and the urban West Midlands, i.e., Birmingham. Flood disadvantaged areas were dispersed but Lincolnshire and The Humber area ranked at the top for all scenarios, followed by areas around the Bristol channel, London, and the southeast coast, and several lower population density areas, such as Isle of Anglesey and the Scottish Lowland.

The analysis of climate actions in the 85 hotspots indicated that 91% had climate action plans in place; however, most of them were mitigation related and only 58% of the LAs had also adaptation plans. When comparing action performances, many of the LAs scored low for adaptation action performances, with 51% of the LAs having performance scores less than 1/8 (compared to 16% for mitigation).

Linking Climate Disadvantage and Adaptation Actions

For heat and flood disadvantages alike, the majority of LAs in greater London, Forest Heath, Nottingham, areas around the Bristol channel, and West Midlands had an adaptation strategy in place or were working on it (e.g., Isle of Anglesey, Lincolnshire, and Hull); therefore, a link of their implementation to vulnerability could be suggested. For example, London has proposed the London Environment Strategy that integrated beside others, the area of adapting to climate change. An implementation plan, produced in 2018, outlined proposed actions and the target that “London and Londoners will be resilient to severe weather and longer-term climate change impacts, such as flooding, heat risk and drought” (London Government, n.d., p. 30). Another example is the Glasgow City Region (which ranks high for flood scenario 4), where

seven of the eight LAs adopted the Climate Ready Clyde Adaptation Strategy, a strategy that seeks to prepare the region for climate impacts and which is supported by an action plan (Climate Ready Clyde, n.d.).

While the LAs in the Liverpool (i.e., Knowsley) and Manchester (i.e., Oldham and Rochdale) areas and Hull, lacked adaptation plans, they are in regions with higher unemployment rates and especially the Liverpool area is considered part of “cities in decline” or “most struggling cities” and thus, albeit more vulnerable, also less likely to have the financial means (Sayers et al., 2017, p. 30). However, a somewhat surprising result was that Boston ranked top 1 for all four flooding scenarios, but it did neither have mitigation, nor adaptation strategies in place. Yet again, they built a large tidal barrier across the River Witham indicating their awareness of the flooding risks.

Possible Reasons for Adaptation Gaps

The results indicated, when comparing the performances for the sections governance/funding, adaptation, and mitigation, the distribution was clearly skewed towards mitigation. Additionally, for LAs with higher performance scores for governance/funding, the focus on mitigation and adaptation was somewhat evenly distributed, whereas for LAs with lower scores, the majority focused on mitigation. These findings suggest that funding could be a limiting factor, more so if less funding is available.

The results also highlighted another performance section, where LAs scored lowly, namely education, skills, and training. Additionally, while 73% of the LAs had a helpful website, not all of them had direct climate change related information. Few LAs acknowledged the risks of heat, and research showed that many houses were and still are being built on floodplains

(Sayers et al., 2017), thus possibly suggesting a lack of knowledge on the extents and future risks of heat and flooding.

This interpretation could be supported by the example of the £100 million Boston tidal barrier (Pollard et al., 2021). Boston had no mitigation or adaptation action plans; however, by building the barrier, they showed that they were aware of the risk, and that lacking funds were not the reason but possibly limited knowledge. The construction of the barrier might have given them a false sense of security; therefore, they decided they did not need adaptation measures. It could be argued that this is a case of maladaptation, where engineered defences “preclude alternative approaches such as EBA”(Ecosystem-based Adaptation) or “adaptation actions [are] not taking wider impacts into account” (Noble et al., p. 858). In any case, knowledge of these possibilities would help them understand that adaptation actions should still be considered.

These findings fit with the theory that in the UK, lacking adaptation actions in most areas have been caused by “gaps in awareness about the risks, the presence of externalities and missing markets, financial constraints, and various behavioural barriers” (CCC, 2021b, p. 18).

Implications

The results presented in this paper built on existing assessments conducted by Lindley et al. (2011) for heat data and Sayers et al. (2017) for flooding data. Whereas the previous heat assessment had focused on larger areas and vulnerability, and used different methods, their hotspot locations largely agreed with these results. Likewise, the flood assessment had focused on *change in disadvantage* only and used different methods. Therefore, not unexpectedly, less than half of the disadvantaged LAs are the same as theirs, demonstrating the importance of understanding different presentation methods.

This paper built upon previous assessment results by presenting maps and tables of the 30 most heat and flood disadvantaged LAs with climate action status, and thus, can aid decision making processes for urban heat management and adaptation fund allocations. Moreover, findings on the status and performance of adaptation actions supplemented the research conducted by Climate Emergency UK (n.d.) and may help identify gaps and support much need improvement regarding adaptation.

Finally, while these results indicated that the vast majority of LAs had climate actions in place, it also highlighted the low performances in most of the categories and that most of the results were combined for mitigation and adaptation, e.g., commitment and integration. These results demonstrate that adaptation plans are not only needed, but they must be implemented, and their success needs to be monitored, because the plan to adapt is just not enough.

Considerations and Limitations

There are various methods to present climate disadvantage. While this paper shows a ranking of categorical data, other research results were ranked using different methods or spatial units, thus making comparison and validation of data difficult. Other factors, that were not considered when ranking the data of future climate disadvantages, are possible changes in vulnerability and hazard-exposure, tipping points in the climate system, and cumulative effects. While the results touched on the fact that of the 85 hotspots in England, 57% had combined heat and flood disadvantages, the LAs were separated into the sections heat and flooding before they were ranked, thus not considering cumulative effects.

The geospatial heat data was only available for England, flooding data for Northern Ireland, and measures of future heatwave were also not available. Future exposure-hazard maps were only available on the mapping tool and needed to be digitized. The lack in data, resulted in

an incomplete picture, when especially Northern Ireland would have been important to consider due to its high vulnerability (Sayers et al, 2017). Moreover, the future heat exposure data used to determine heat disadvantage was based on outdated 2009 UK Climate Projections at low resolution. Additionally, predictive climate models in general make local interpretation difficult due to several factors, including natural processes, greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, regional circulation patterns and local land features (Lindley et al., 2011).

Despite these limitations, results are nonetheless valid for the purpose of answering the questions of the locations of the top 30 most disadvantaged local authorities for each scenario and their state of adaptation actions. While the results do not show a complete and dependable future picture (considering future uncertainties), the presented areas and results are complete and reproducible, and highlight disadvantaged areas at current spatial and temporal scales.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This research aimed to identify and map the top 30 most disadvantaged local authorities regarding future heat hazards in England and future flooding hazards in GB, analyse the state of any adaptation actions in those locations, and suggest reasons for possible adaptation gaps. The results of the quantitative analysis of climate disadvantages indicated relatively high to acute heat risks for the urban areas, such as greater London, and high to extreme flood risks to numerous LAs across GB, with highest ranks for Boston, and The Humber, Lincolnshire, and Bristol channel areas.

By analyzing adaptation actions and climate performances for the 85 most disadvantaged LAs across GB, this research has shown that by February 2022, 91% had climate action plans or strategies in place; however, most of them were mitigation related. Just over half of the LAs had also adaptation plans, and out of those, again, about half achieved very low scores for adaptation

action performance. Based on these results, funding and possibly knowledge gaps were identified as limiting factors and barriers to adaptation.

These results demonstrated that, while there are climate actions in place, their performance scores in most of the categories were low and most of the results were combined for mitigation and adaptation, e.g., commitment and integration. These results demonstrate that adaptation plans are not only needed, but they must be implemented, their performance scores need to improve, and their success needs to be monitored to be able to learn from outcomes and improve the adaptation planning processes.

This research also found that in GB, the focus was on flood management and very little on heat. It raised the question why heatwaves have been perceived as a greater climate concern than particularly warm summers (Porter et al., 2015), yet there has been little robust evidence base, and it focused on England only (Brimicombe et al., 2021), mirroring some experiences of this paper. While heatwaves can be drivers for governments to act (Tompkins et al., 2010), management policies again focused on England (Brimicombe et al., 2021). Further research is needed across all UK countries, to ensure the risks posed by heatwaves are recognized for multiple sectors and to progress just adaptation actions at all government levels.

This research built upon two previous heat and flood vulnerability assessments and presented maps and tables of the altogether 85 most heat and flood disadvantaged LAs with their climate action statuses, to be considered in decision-making processes to better identify LAs most in need. Moreover, findings on the status and performance of adaptation actions supplemented existing research, not only confirming the disconnect between vulnerability mapping and adaptive responses (Preston et al., 2011), but also identifying their locations, thus, supporting targeted improvement of adaptation actions and performances.

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Figures

Figure 1

Government Structure and Proposed Study Areas

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, Scottish Government. In the public domain.

Figure 2*Socio-Spatial Heat Vulnerability in England*

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority. Heat analysis from “Climate change, justice, and vulnerability”, by Lindley, S. J., O’Neill, J., Kandeh, J., Lawson, N., Christian, R., and O’Neill, M. (2011). C. Joseph Rowntree Foundation Report, York. <http://www.jrf.org.uk/publications/climate-change-justiceand-vulnerability>. Data derived from Climate Just Heat Maps. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 3

Projected Heat Disadvantage (Four Scenarios)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, UK Climate Projections 2009 (Crown copyright); Heat analysis by Lindley et al. (2011). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 4

Socio-Spatial Flood Vulnerability in Great Britain

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, Scottish Government. Flood vulnerability analysis by Sayers et al. (2017). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 5*Projected Fluvial and Coastal Flood Disadvantage (Individual and Group)*

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, Scottish Government. Flood risk analysis by Sayers et al. (2017). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 6

Projected Pluvial (Surface Water) Flood Disadvantage (Individual and Group)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, Scottish Government. Flood risk analysis by Sayers et al. (2017). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 7

Analytical Framework for Mapping and Analyzing Adaptation Policies in the Top 30 Disadvantaged Local Authorities

Disadvantaged Local Authorities

Figure 8

Ranks of the 30 Most Heat Disadvantaged Local Authorities (Average Vulnerability and mean summer maximum temperature 2050s)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, UK Climate Projections 2009 (Crown copyright); Heat analysis by Lindley et al. (2011). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 9

Ranks of the 30 Most Heat Disadvantaged Local Authorities (Neighbourhood-weighted vulnerability and mean summer maximum temperature 2050s)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, UK Climate Projections 2009 (Crown copyright); Heat analysis by Lindley et al. (2011). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 10

Ranks of the 30 Most Heat Disadvantaged Local Authorities (Average vulnerability and change in mean summer maximum temperature baseline to 2050s)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, UK Climate Projections 2009 (Crown copyright); Heat analysis by Lindley et al. (2011). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 11

Ranks of the 30 Most Heat Disadvantaged Local Authorities (Neighbourhood-weighted vulnerability and change in mean summer maximum temperature baseline to 2050s)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, UK Climate Projections 2009 (Crown copyright); Heat analysis by Lindley et al. (2011). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 12

Ranks of the 30 Most Flood Disadvantaged Local Authorities (Group SFRI , Fluvial and Coastal, and 2050s 4°C Future)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, Scottish Government. Flood risk analysis by Sayers et al. (2017). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 13

Ranks of the 30 Most Flood Disadvantaged Local Authorities (Individual iSFRI, Fluvial and Coastal, and 2050s 4°C Future)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, Scottish Government. Flood risk analysis by Sayers et al. (2017). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 14

Ranks of the 30 Most Flood Disadvantaged Local Authorities (Group SFRI, Surface Water, and 2050s 4°C Future)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, Scottish Government. Flood risk analysis by Sayers et al. (2017). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 15

Ranks of the 30 Most Flood Disadvantaged Local Authorities (Individual iSFRI, Surface Water, and 2050s 4°C Future)

Note. Spatial data sources are Esri, Michael Bauer Research GmbH, Office for National Statistics (ONS)/UK Statistics Authority, Scottish Government. Flood risk analysis by Sayers et al. (2017). From mapping tool by Climate Just. <https://www.climatejust.org.uk/map>. In the public domain.

Figure 16

Normal Distributions of Climate Action Performance Scores for Mitigation and Adaptation Combined and Governance, Development, and Funding (in Great Britain)

Figure 17

Spatial Distribution of Climate Action Performance Scores Across Local Authorities for Mitigation and Adaptation and for Governance, Development, and Funding

Note. Other = LA merged into another LA since 2017. Office for National Statistics (ONS).

Adapted from “Council Climate Plan Scorecards”, by Climate Emergency UK (n.d.-a).

<https://councilclimatescorecards.uk>. In the public domain.

Figure 18

Spatial Distribution of Climate Action Performance Scores Across Most Disadvantaged Local Authorities for Mitigation and Adaptation

Note. Office for National Statistics (ONS). Adapted from “Council Climate Plan Scorecards”, by Climate Emergency UK (n.d.-a). <https://councilclimatescorecards.uk>. In the public domain.

Figure 19

Normal Distributions of Climate Action Performance Scores for Mitigation, Adaptation, and Governance, Development, and Funding (in Hotspots)

Tables

Table 1

Ranks of Most Disadvantaged Local Authorities to Two Heat Hazard-Exposure Measures (Mean Summer Maximum Temperature in the 2050s)

Scenario 1			Scenario 3		
Average Vulnerability			Neighbourhood-Weighted Vulnerability		
Local Authority	%NV	Rank	Local Authority	%NV	Rank
Newham	22.6	1	Newham	22.6	1
Tower Hamlets	22.2	2	Tower Hamlets	22.2	2
Barking and Dagenham	18.2	3	Barking and Dagenham	18.2	3
Westminster	18.0	4	Westminster	18.0	4
Forest Heath	17.6	5	Forest Heath	17.6	5
Haringey	17.2	6	Haringey	17.2	6
Brent	16.8	7	Brent	16.8	7
Southwark	16.3	8	Southwark	16.3	8
Hackney	16.0	9	Hackney	16.0	9
Nottingham	15.8	10	Nottingham	15.8	10
Waltham Forest	15.3	11	Waltham Forest	15.3	11
Hammersmith and Fulham	15.0	12	Hammersmith and Fulham	15.0	12
Lewisham	14.8	13	Lewisham	14.8	13
Islington	14.6	14	Islington	14.6	14
Birmingham	13.8	15	Birmingham	13.6	15
Kensington and Chelsea	13.6	16	Kensington and Chelsea	13.6	16

Camden	13.5	17	Camden	13.5	17
Lambeth	13.5	18	Lambeth	13.5	18
Leicester	13.0	19	Sandwell	12.8	19
Sandwell	12.8	20	Coventry	12.8	20
Coventry	12.8	21	Ealing	12.8	21
Ealing	12.8	22	Hounslow	12.7	22
Hounslow	12.7	23	Greenwich	12.6	23
Greenwich	12.6	24	Knowsley	12.2	24
Knowsley	12.2	25	Oxford	12.0	25
Kingston upon Hull, City of	12.0	26	Wolverhampton	12.0	26
Oxford	12.0	27	Cambridge	11.4	27
Wolverhampton	12.0	28	Liverpool	11.1	28
York	11.7	29	Luton	10.7	29
Cambridge	11.4	30	Croydon	10.5	30

Note. Rank = Rank of most disadvantaged local authorities, %NV = most socially vulnerable neighbourhoods as a proportion of the total number of neighbourhoods within each local authority (in %)

Table 2

*Ranks of Top 30 Most Disadvantaged Local Authorities to Two Heat Hazard-Exposure Measures
(Change in Mean Summer Maximum Temperature From the Climate Baseline to the 2050s)*

Scenario 2			Scenario 4		
Average Vulnerability			Neighbourhood-Weighted Vulnerability		
Local Authority	%NV	Rank	Local Authority	%NV	Rank
Newham	22.6	1	Newham	22.6	1
Tower Hamlets	22.2	2	Tower Hamlets	22.2	2
Barking and Dagenham	18.2	3	Barking and Dagenham	18.2	3
Westminster	18.0	4	Westminster	18.0	4
Haringey	17.2	5	Haringey	17.2	5
Brent	16.8	6	Brent	16.8	6
Southwark	16.3	7	Southwark	16.3	7
Hackney	16.0	8	Hackney	16.0	8
Nottingham	15.8	9	Waltham Forest	15.3	9
Waltham Forest	15.3	10	Hammersmith and Fulham	15.0	10
Hammersmith and Fulham	15.0	11	Lewisham	14.8	11
Lewisham	14.8	12	Islington	14.6	12
Islington	14.6	13	Birmingham	13.6	13
Birmingham	13.6	14	Kensington and Chelsea	13.6	14
Kensington and Chelsea	13.6	15	Camden	13.5	15
Camden	13.5	16	Lambeth	13.5	16
Lambeth	13.5	17	Sandwell	12.8	17

Leicester	13.0	18	Coventry	12.8	18
Sandwell	12.8	19	Ealing	12.8	19
Coventry	12.8	20	Hounslow	12.7	20
Ealing	12.8	21	Greenwich	12.6	21
Hounslow	12.7	22	Manchester	12.4	22
Greenwich	12.6	23	Wolverhampton	12.0	23
Manchester	12.4	24	Croydon	10.5	24
Oxford	12.0	25	Redbridge	9.9	25
Wolverhampton	12.0	26	Oldham	9.9	26
Forest Heath	11.8	27	Enfield	9.8	27
Middlesbrough	11.6	28	Rochdale	9.7	28
Cambridge	11.4	29	Hillingdon	9.3	29
Luton	10.7	30	Slough	8.8	30

Note. Rank = Rank of most disadvantaged local authority for this scenario, %NV = most socially vulnerable neighbourhoods as a proportion of the total number of neighbourhoods within each local authority (in %)

Table 3

Ranks of Top 30 Most Disadvantaged Local Authorities to Fluvial and Coastal Flooding (2050s 4°C Future)

Scenario 1			Scenario 3		
Neighbourhood Scale 'Group' Measure			'Individual' Scale		
Local Authority	%NV	Rank	Local Authority	%NV	Rank
Boston	100.0	1	Boston	100.0	1
Kingston upon Hull, City of	60.2	2	Isle of Anglesey	77.3	2
East Lindsey	39.5	3	West Somerset	76.2	3
West Somerset	38.1	4	East Lindsey	58.0	4
Newham	36.0	5	Kingston upon Hull, City of	56.6	5
Shepway	35.8	6	Shepway	52.2	6
Southwark	34.9	7	West Lindsey	50.0	7
Sedgemoor	31.4	8	Rhondda Cynon Taf	44.2	8
North East Lincolnshire	31.1	9	Neath Port Talbot	42.9	9
Hammersmith and Fulham	28.3	10	Blaenau Gwent	42.6	10
West Lindsey	25.0	11	Newham	40.9	11
Great Yarmouth	24.6	12	Southwark	39.8	12
South Holland	22.4	13	Hammersmith and Fulham	35.4	13
Eastbourne	21.3	14	Great Yarmouth	34.4	14
Swale	21.2	15	Carmarthenshire	33.9	15
Slough	20.0	16	Merthyr Tydfil	33.3	16
Leicester	18.2	17	Swale	32.9	17

Barking and Dagenham	18.2	18	North East Lincolnshire	32.1	18
Newport	17.9	19	Sedgemoor	31.4	19
North Somerset	17.0	20	Newport	28.4	20
Lewisham	16.6	21	Slough	27.5	21
Warrington	16.5	22	Bridgend	27.3	22
Tower Hamlets	16.0	23	East Ayrshire	27.0	23
Greenwich	15.9	24	Barking and Dagenham	25.5	24
King's Lynn and West Norfolk	14.6	25	Dumfries and Galloway	25.4	25
Neath Port Talbot	14.3	26	Leicester	25.0	26
Thurrock	14.3	27	Torfaen	25.0	27
Conwy	14.1	28	Lewisham	24.9	28
Denbighshire	13.8	29	Orkney Islands	24.1	29
Runnymede	13.5	30	Teignbridge	23.8	30

Note. Assuming continuing adaptation efforts and high population growth.

Table 4

*Ranks of Top 30 Most Disadvantaged Local Authorities to Pluvial (Surface Water) Flooding
(2050s 4°C Future)*

Scenario 2			Scenario 4		
Neighbourhood Scale 'Group' Measure			'Individual' Scale		
Local Authority	%NV	Rank	Local Authority	%NV	Rank
Boston	100.0	1	Boston	91.7	1
Blaenau Gwent	95.7	2	Blaenau Gwent	89.4	2
Newham	94.5	3	Isle of Anglesey	81.8	3
Barking and Dagenham	93.6	4	West Somerset	81.0	4
Isle of Anglesey	93.2	5	Rhondda Cynon Taf	73.4	5
West Lindsey	92.3	6	East Ayrshire	70.6	6
Shepway	91.0	7	Hammersmith and Fulham	66.4	7
Merthyr Tydfil	86.1	8	Shepway	65.7	8
West Somerset	85.7	9	Kensington and Chelsea	65.0	9
Brent	85.5	10	Tower Hamlets	64.6	10
Waltham Forest	84.0	11	North Ayrshire	63.4	11
East Lindsey	84.0	12	Glasgow City	63.3	12
Rhondda Cynon Taf	83.8	13	West Dunbartonshire	62.8	13
Hackney	81.9	14	Leicester	60.9	14
Leicester	78.1	15	Clackmannanshire	58.3	15
Tower Hamlets	77.1	16	Merthyr Tydfil	58.3	16
Sandwell	75.9	17	Blackburn with Darwen	58.2	17

Hammersmith and Fulham	74.3	18	Barking and Dagenham	58.2	18
Kensington and Chelsea	72.8	19	East Lindsey	58.0	19
Neath Port Talbot	70.3	20	North Lanarkshire	57.3	20
Slough	70.0	21	Bristol, City of	57.0	21
Hastings	69.8	22	Hackney	56.9	22
East Ayrshire	69.3	23	Brent	56.6	23
Wolverhampton	68.4	24	Inverclyde	56.6	24
Burnley	68.3	25	Dundee City	56.4	25
Islington	67.5	26	Renfrewshire	55.8	26
Swale	67.1	27	Wolverhampton	55.7	27
Haringey	66.9	28	Slough	55.0	28
Nottingham	66.7	29	West Lindsey	53.8	29
Thanet	66.7	30	Dumfries and Galloway	53.2	30

Note. Assuming continuing adaptation efforts and high population growth.

Table 5

State of Adaptation Actions in the 85 Most Disadvantaged Local Authorities (As of February 2022)

Local Authority	Scorecard Section (SS) or Category (C)									
	SS1	C1	C2	SS2.1	SS2.2	C3	SS3	C4	C5	SS4
Barking and Dagenham	24%	2	2	13%	50%	2	43%	0	0	33%
Birmingham	52%	2	2	25%	80%	2	57%	2	1	56%
Blackburn with Darwen	38%	2	2	63%	30%	2	43%	2	1	67%
Blaenau Gwent	10%	2	2	25%	20%	2	0%	0	0	22%
Boston	0%	1	1	0%	0%	2	29%	2	0	33%
Brent	67%	2	2	75%	80%	2	86%	2	1	67%
Bridgend	No action plan on February 11, 2022									
Bristol, City of	71%	2	2	50%	100%	2	14%	2	1	56%
Burnley	No action plan on February 11, 2022									
Cambridge	48%	2	2	50%	90%	2	86%	2	1	78%
Camden	67%	2	2	13%	50%	2	86%	2	1	67%
Carmarthenshire	48%	2	2	13%	10%	2	71%	2	0	33%
Clackmannanshire	No action plan on February 11, 2022									
Conwy	5%	0	2	0%	0%	2	0%	0	0	22%
Coventry	No action plan on February 11, 2022									
Croydon	52%	2	2	25%	60%	2	71%	0	1	56%
Denbighshire	43%	2	2	13%	20%	2	86%	2	1	78%
Dumfries and Galloway	67%	0	2	0%	0%	2	14%	0	0	11%
Dundee City	52%	2	2	88%	70%	2	57%	2	1	56%
Ealing	57%	2	2	38%	70%	2	100%	2	1	100%
East Ayrshire	19%	0	2	0%	50%	0	14%	0	1	56%
East Lindsey	48%	0	2	0%	10%	0	43%	0	0	33%
Eastbourne	43%	2	2	13%	70%	2	86%	2	0	44%
Enfield	57%	2	2	38%	50%	2	71%	2	1	67%
Forest Heath	81%	2	2	38%	90%	2	71%	2	1	67%
Glasgow City	76%	2	2	25%	90%	2	86%	2	1	78%
Great Yarmouth	No action plan on February 11, 2022									
Greenwich	76%	2	2	13%	100%	2	71%	0	1	56%
Hackney	No action plan on February 11, 2022									
Hammersmith and Fulham	81%	2	2	100%	100%	2	71%	2	1	78%
Haringey	71%	2	2	38%	80%	2	86%	2	1	67%
Hastings	38%	2	2	13%	40%	2	57%	0	1	56%
Hillingdon	33%	2	2	13%	40%	2	29%	0	1	89%
Hounslow	71%	2	2	50%	60%	0	86%	2	1	78%

Inverclyde	24%	2	2	0%	20%	0	29%	2	0	11%	
Isle of Anglesey											
Islington	71%	0	2	0%	80%	2	71%	0	1	89%	
Kensington and Chelsea	43%	2	2	38%	100%	2	71%	2	0	44%	
King's Lynn and West Norfolk	38%	0	2	0%	20%	2	14%	0	1	56%	
Kingston upon Hull	33%	1	2	13%	90%	2	43%	2	1	67%	
Knowsley	43%	0	2	0%	0%	2	57%	0	0	22%	
Lambeth	33%	0	2	0%	30%	2	57%	0	0	44%	
Leicester	90%	2	2	63%	100%	2	86%	2	1	100%	
Lewisham	71%	2	2	63%	60%	2	100%	2	1	78%	
Liverpool	38%	0	2	0%	40%	2	14%	0	0	11%	
Luton	10%	2	2	0%	0%	2	57%	2	0	33%	
Manchester	90%	2	2	100%	100%	2	86%	2	1	78%	
Merthyr Tydfil	10%	0	2	0%	0%	0	14%	0	0	22%	
Middlesbrough	29%	0	2	0%	40%	2	14%	2	0	33%	
Neath Port Talbot	19%	2	2	25%	40%	0	71%	0	0	33%	
Newham	33%	2	2	13%	60%	2	71%	2	1	89%	
Newport	48%	0	2	0%	10%	2	14%	0	0	11%	
North Ayrshire	43%	2	2	13%	50%	2	43%	2	0	33%	
North East Lincolnshire				No action plan on February 11, 2022							
North Lanarkshire	67%	2	2	38%	90%	2	43%	2	0	33%	
North Somerset	38%	2	2	13%	50%	2	14%	2	0	33%	
Nottingham	67%	2	2	63%	100%	2	86%	0	1	56%	
Oldham	14%	0	2	0%	20%	2	29%	0	1	67%	
Orkney Islands	33%	0	2	0%	10%	2	0%	0	0	22%	
Oxford	52%	2	2	50%	50%	2	86%	0	0	44%	
Redbridge	52%	0	2	0%	60%	2	71%	0	1	56%	
Renfrewshire				No action plan on February 11, 2022							
Rhondda Cynon Taf	29%	2	2	38%	90%	0	57%	0	0	44%	
Rochdale	10%	0	2	0%	10%	2	0%	0	0	22%	
Runnymede				No action plan on February 11, 2022							
Sandwell	76%	2	2	75%	70%	2	43%	2	1	67%	
Sedgemoor	62%	2	2	100%	100%	2	57%	2	1	67%	
Shepway	71%	2	2	25%	80%	2	86%	2	1	56%	
Slough	62%	2	2	88%	100%	0	57%	2	1	67%	
South Holland				No action plan on February 11, 2022							
Southwark	76%	2	2	88%	100%	2	57%	2	1	89%	
Swale	62%	2	2	50%	90%	2	86%	0	1	67%	
Teignbridge	38%	0	2	0%	90%	2	43%	2	1	56%	
Thanet	48%	2	2	38%	90%	2	71%	0	1	78%	
Thurrock				No action plan on February 11, 2022							

Torfaen				No action plan on February 11, 2022						
Tower Hamlets	52%	0	2	0%	40%	2	43%	2	0	33%
Waltham Forest				No action plan on February 11, 2022						
Warrington	43%	0	2	0%	30%	2	14%	0	1	56%
West Dunbartonshire	52%	2	2	50%	60%	2	100%	2	1	78%
West Lindsey	67%	2	2	63%	70%	0	43%	0	1	78%
West Somerset	81%	2	2	100%	100%	2	100%	2	1	89%
Westminster	52%	1	2	0%	100%	2	43%	2	1	78%
Wolverhampton	19%	0	2	0%	20%	2	14%	0	1	56%
York				No action plan on February 11, 2022						
Average	48%	1	2	29%	57%	2	54%	1	1	55%

Note. C = Category, based on criteria derived from literature review. C1 = Adaptation strategy/action plan for heat/flooding in place. C2 = Climate strategy, mitigation, or carbon reduction plan in place. C3 = Passed climate emergency declaration. C4 = Other adaptation actions. C5 = Website easy to navigate and helpful. 0 = Not evident/sufficient. 1 = No, but in progress. 2 = Yes.

SS = Climate Emergency UK Scorecard Section. SS1 = Governance, Development and Funding. SS2.1 = Adaptation. SS2.2 = Mitigation. SS3 = Commitment and Integration. SS4 = Community Engagement and Communications. % = Climate action performance in per cent. Adapted from “Council Climate Plan Scorecards” by Climate Emergency UK, n.d.-a, (<https://councilclimatescorecards.uk/methodology/#sec-gov>). In the public domain.

Table 6*Climate Action Performance Scores for the 85 Most Disadvantaged Local Authorities**(December 2021)*

Local Authority	Total Score	Scorecard Section (SS)				
		SS5	SS6	SS7	SS8	SS9
Barking and Dagenham	34%	40%	75%	40%	0%	50%
Birmingham	53%	60%	75%	40%	40%	50%
Blackburn with Darwen	41%	60%	75%	0%	0%	50%
Blaenau Gwent	17%	80%	25%	0%	0%	0%
Boston	13%	20%	0%	0%	0%	25%
Brent	73%	40%	100%	80%	80%	75%
Bridgend	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Bristol, City of	64%	100%	100%	20%	100%	75%
Burnley	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Cambridge	64%	80%	75%	60%	0%	75%
Camden	61%	80%	100%	20%	60%	50%
Carmarthenshire	32%	40%	25%	0%	20%	0%
Clackmannanshire	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Conwy	6%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Coventry	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Croydon	60%	60%	100%	60%	60%	75%
Denbighshire	47%	40%	0%	0%	60%	75%
Dumfries and Galloway	20%	40%	0%	0%	20%	0%
Dundee City	63%	80%	100%	60%	40%	75%
Ealing	73%	80%	50%	40%	80%	75%
East Ayrshire	35%	80%	25%	0%	60%	50%
East Lindsey	25%	40%	25%	0%	0%	0%
Eastbourne	50%	100%	50%	0%	20%	50%
Enfield	46%	60%	25%	0%	0%	50%
Forest Heath	64%	80%	75%	0%	60%	75%
Glasgow City	75%	60%	100%	40%	100%	100%
Great Yarmouth	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Greenwich	64%	80%	75%	20%	80%	50%
Hackney	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Hammersmith and Fulham	80%	100%	100%	20%	100%	75%
Haringey	69%	100%	50%	40%	60%	75%
Hastings	42%	80%	75%	0%	0%	75%
Hillingdon	42%	60%	25%	0%	40%	75%
Hounslow	65%	40%	75%	40%	80%	25%
Inverclyde	20%	40%	0%	0%	40%	25%

Isle of Anglesey	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Islington	62%	80%	50%	20%	40%	75%
Kensington and Chelsea	62%	60%	100%	60%	80%	50%
King's Lynn and West Norfolk	26%	60%	0%	0%	20%	0%
Kingston upon Hull	50%	100%	50%	20%	40%	25%
Knowsley	24%	40%	0%	0%	20%	0%
Lambeth	37%	80%	50%	0%	0%	75%
Leicester	71%	80%	75%	0%	20%	75%
Lewisham	77%	60%	100%	80%	80%	75%
Liverpool	23%	40%	25%	0%	20%	50%
Luton	19%	0%	0%	0%	40%	0%
Manchester	87%	60%	100%	80%	100%	100%
Merthyr Tydfil	9%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Middlesbrough	25%	20%	75%	0%	20%	50%
Neath Port Talbot	33%	40%	25%	0%	0%	75%
Newham	52%	40%	75%	40%	40%	25%
Newport	13%	0%	25%	0%	0%	0%
North Ayrshire	37%	60%	0%	0%	60%	50%
North East Lincolnshire	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
North Lanarkshire	52%	60%	25%	60%	40%	75%
North Somerset	33%	80%	25%	0%	20%	75%
Nottingham	76%	100%	100%	40%	100%	75%
Oldham	34%	20%	50%	20%	80%	25%
Orkney Islands	11%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Oxford	48%	80%	25%	20%	20%	0%
Redbridge	53%	40%	100%	20%	60%	75%
Renfrewshire	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Rhondda Cynon Taf	43%	40%	25%	0%	40%	75%
Rochdale	11%	20%	50%	0%	0%	25%
Runnymede	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Sandwell	61%	40%	100%	0%	100%	75%
Sedgemoor	71%	60%	100%	20%	100%	100%
Shepway	59%	60%	100%	20%	20%	75%
Slough	66%	80%	75%	20%	60%	75%
South Holland	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Southwark	79%	100%	75%	60%	80%	75%
Swale	64%	80%	100%	40%	0%	75%
Teignbridge	42%	40%	50%	0%	40%	75%
Thanet	58%	20%	100%	20%	60%	75%
Thurrock	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Torfaen	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Tower Hamlets	34%	40%	75%	0%	0%	75%

Waltham Forest	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Warrington	31%	40%	25%	0%	40%	50%
West Dunbartonshire	55%	40%	0%	0%	60%	50%
West Lindsey	54%	60%	75%	0%	40%	50%
West Somerset	92%	100%	100%	60%	100%	100%
Westminster	57%	60%	75%	40%	60%	50%
Wolverhampton	24%	60%	0%	0%	0%	50%
York	0%	No action plan on September 20, 2021				
Average	39%	57%	54%	19%	41%	53%

Note. SS5 = Measuring and Setting Emissions Targets. SS6 = Co-benefits. SS7 = Diversity and Social Inclusion. SS8 = Education, Skills and Training. SS9 = Ecological Emergency.

% = Climate action performance in per cent. Adapted from “Council Climate Plan Scorecards” by Climate Emergency UK, n.d.-a, (<https://councilclimatescorecards.uk/methodology/#sec-gov>).

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